

Marjorie-Roxana ANDRADE-VELÁSQUEZ

Pontifical Catholic University of Ecuador, Santo Domingo. Ecuador. avmr@pucesd.edu.ec
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7853-733X>

Dra. M. Carmen FONSECA-MORA

COIDESO Research Centre, University of Huelva, Spain. fonseca@uhu.es
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2404-3553>

Transmedia storytelling in foreign language learning

Las narrativas transmedia en el aprendizaje de lenguas extranjeras

Dates | Received: 22/09/2020 - Reviewed: 01/01/2021 - In press: 21/02/2021 - Published final: 01/07/2021

Abstract

Transmedia education has burst into the educational field in recent years generating new forms of active student-centred learning. However, its effectiveness and how it affects foreign language learning is still unknown. This article reviews studies of the application of Transmedia Storytelling or Transmedia Narratives to detail the benefits of the result of its application and the main achievements reached by students in learning foreign languages. This qualitative synthesis, which arises from the review of studies published on the matter from 2010 to 2020, allows us to describe the current state of the issue and to recommend this innovative methodological technique in the educational context for the development of the linguistic competences of a foreign language.

Keywords

Transmedia Narratives; Innovation; Motivation; Competencies; Learning foreign languages

Resumen

La educación transmedia ha irrumpido en el campo educativo en los últimos años generando nuevas formas de aprendizaje activo centrado en los estudiantes. Sin embargo, aún se desconoce su efectividad y cómo afecta al aprendizaje de lenguas extranjeras. En este artículo se revisa de manera sistemática estudios de la aplicación de Transmedia Storytelling o Narrativas Transmedia para detallar los beneficios del resultado de su aplicación y los principales logros alcanzados por los estudiantes en el aprendizaje de lenguas extranjeras. Esta síntesis cualitativa, que surge de la revisión de estudios publicados al respecto desde el año 2010 al 2020, permite describir el estado actual de la cuestión y recomendar esta innovadora técnica metodológica en el contexto educativo para el desarrollo de las competencias lingüísticas de una lengua extranjera.

Palabras clave

Narrativas Transmedia; Innovación; Motivación; Competencias; Aprendizaje de lenguas extranjeras

1. Introduction

21st Century society requires a transformation in teaching methodologies which can allow students to develop their learning in spaces where they can generate new experiences and improve the skills needed for a society in constant flux. Language learning is an important tool that contributes to academic and professional progress. In fact, two of the essential 21st Century skills, which promote access to and mobility within the labour market, are communicative competency in several languages, especially English, Spanish and Chinese, and digital competency (Buyse & Fonseca, 2017).

Learning a second language is a complicated process. Even if some people master it fairly easily, other slower learners encounter multiple difficulties. Noticeable among these difficulties, is the students' level of demotivation, because foreign language learning is a process which requires the use of innovative elements which attract students' attention and awaken their curiosity for learning (Cores, Fernández-Corbacho, Machancoses & Fonseca-Mora, 2019). Without a doubt, the teacher's role is essential in the selection of activities which encourage interaction and in the choice of motivational teaching techniques. The educator's role focusses fundamentally on promoting group dynamics and on taking responsibility for organising activities, for motivating and for creating a pleasant learning environment (Paulsen, 1992 in Silva, 2010). Moreover, by supporting our students to develop their creativity, curiosity, independence and critical thinking skills, these can become transferrable skills, which are useful in all fields of knowledge for their professional and personal future (Sánchez Vizcaíno & Fonseca-Mora, 2020). These skills are linked to the development of digital competencies which contribute to the connectivity of users in this globalised world, where our communicative spaces have expanded exponentially. Furthermore, digital media may encourage independent learning, inside and outside the modern languages classroom (Buyse & Fonseca, 2017).

Among the current tendencies in the field of language teaching are the use of learner-centred approaches which are motivational and attractive for the students. These methodologies encourage students to reflect on their own learning processes. In other words, there is a whole range of innovative methodologies in language teaching, such as the Theory of Multiple Intelligences (Fonseca, 2002), Content and Language Integrated Learning, CLIL (Carrillo & López, 2014; Griva & Deligianni, 2017), or other *avant-garde* methodologies like Project-Based Learning (Trujillo, 2017), the Flipped Classroom (Turan & Akdag-Cimen, 2019), Visual thinking (Cappello & Walker, 2016), or Gamification (Mira, 2017).

Carbonell (2001) defines innovation as a series of interventions, decisions and processes, with a certain degree of intentionality and systematisation, which attempt to modify attitudes, ideas, cultures, contents, models and pedagogical practices. These interventions, decisions and processes also aim to introduce new projects and programmes, curriculum materials, teaching and learning strategies, didactic models and other ways of organising and managing the curriculum, the centre and classroom dynamics. Thus, innovation consists of introducing modifications to improve the final result (Aguar, Velásquez & Aguilar, 2019) and involves transforming our educational practices in creative ways, whilst maintaining the objective of obtaining effective learning outcomes (Maquilón, 2011). This contemporary educational perspective, combined with the frequent use of platforms and social media networks, has given rise to *Transmedia Storytelling* (Scolari, 2013), an innovation which seeks to motivate learners by incorporating them not only as consumers but also as active producers of messages across different media. This role of the foreign language learner as a *prosumer* can be very advantageous to the teaching and learning process as it allows for the generation of learning contexts which mirror students' daily lives. This is done by using many different media and prompting the interaction between multiple users. The immersive nature of this approach, together with the use of different platforms, can attract learners who are familiar with digital environments and multimedia, and therefore, serve as a motivating factor.

The objective of this paper is, thus, to review existing findings on Transmedia Storytelling (TS) to find out how it has been applied to language teaching and to the development of communicative competencies. The aim of this analysis is to qualitatively categorise the benefits described as having resulted directly from the application of this technique to foreign language learning.

1.1. Transmedia storytelling

Transmedia Storytelling (TS) can be understood as a story explained from different perspectives, depending on the medium of communication used. Jenkins (2003:10), who is credited with founding this concept, has stated that: "a transmedia story is developed across multiple media platforms, and each new passage makes a specific and valuable contribution to the whole". He also claims that we are entering a new era in the convergence of media which makes the flow of contents across multiple channels inevitable. According to Jenkins (2003:18) children who have grown up consuming and enjoying *Pokémon* through various media expect the same experience with *The West Wing of the White House* as they grow older.

On the other hand, Scolari (2013: 5) defines TS as “a narrative form in which the story unfolds across multiple media and communication platforms and in which a portion of the consumers assume an active role in the expansion process.” In this way, TS can be said to be characterised by two traits: the expansion of a narrative and a culture of participation (Scolari, 2013). A large part of Jenkins' academic work (2003) has been concerned with the culture of participation. He has focussed on developing a theory of the principles of media practice, whereby users see themselves primarily as active and creative participants. This commitment to participate is regarded as increasingly important, due to the greater capacity for interactive communication brought about by the internet through digital technologies. Moreover, Scolari (2013: 20) adds that TS “is a particular narrative form that expands across different systems of meaning (verbal, iconic, audio-visual, interactive, etc.) and media (cinema, comics, television, video games, theatre, etc.)”. In other words, TS offers the potential of a story being told by means of different codes and in different spaces, making way for new creations which go beyond the change of formats.

Roccanti & Garland (2015) state that TS has transformed teaching methods and, informed by their literature review, they suggest following the steps below for a transmedia strategy.

1. Recognise opportunities for integrating transmedia channels and content for use in the classroom. For example, use different parts of a story to connect the narration and broaden the experience for the student.
2. Provide a clear and simple connection point for users. For example, use a website or forum to facilitate readers' access to and creation of texts and channels. This avoids them having to move between multiple spaces and sites.
3. Encourage students to work together so that discussions can take place whilst they synthesise and connect elements using transmedia threads. For example, allow users to connect with one another, to discuss and reflect on how these narratives, including ones which are not specifically educational, are connected and can bring an account to life.
4. Allow users to recreate, remix and respond to the content in a transmedia thread. For example, inspire students to identify how they can become the authors of their own transmedia stories and expand the narratives in line with the learning objectives of the course.
5. Focus on the narrative and not on the technology, by working with media which are familiar to both the teacher and the learners. By concentrating on the learning objectives, students will focus directly on the tasks in hand, on problem solving and on the critical analysis of the course content.

In this digital era, the fast-changing picture of media technology needs to be incorporated into traditional teaching methods. TS offers a new opportunity to develop a different type of learning and a new way of designing learning experiences for our foreign language courses.

1.2. The role of transmedia practices in the development of linguistic competencies

Having a variety of different tools for developing linguistic skill and proficiency can increase motivation for learning a language. Schumann (2000) described the neural mechanism for the positive or negative evaluation of any stimulus in language learning. He compared the psychological perspective with that of research into second language acquisition, using the former's assessment scales and the latter's motivation questionnaires. He concluded that the following assessment indicators showed that learners feel motivated to do a task: the novelty as well as the familiarity of the task, whether it is to their liking or not, whether it suits their goals or needs, whether they would feel capable of tackling it and whether they can maintain their social image in front of other people. As far as TS is concerned, this new method of learning suits students who acquire new learning competencies via creative production and cooperation in connected learning environments (Ito, 2010) which link up teaching at school and at home and where, by collaborating, students can together obtain better results.

Transmedia practices promote multi-literacy, that is, they imply the development of a new pedagogical practice that focusses on the development of a meta language which includes different multi-modal and communicative channels. Communication media play an important role in the cognitive, social and emotional make-up of its users. (Jenkins, Ford & Green, 2013). Digital media open the door to a new educational paradigm in which learning can take place anywhere, outside the classroom. Daily life becomes a space for new pedagogies and new learning habits. The use of digital technologies has provided an opportunity for carrying out new forms of social interaction, which are currently transforming the role and functioning of formal education institutions, particularly schools and universities (Malone & Bernstein, 2015).

Proposing *Transmedia storytelling* as a didactic strategy for language teaching does not mean adapting one language to another (for example, books to cinema), but it entails learning in a narrative world, which embraces different media and the understanding of different types of language. Thus, “the account is expanded [and] new characters and situations appear, which transcend the boundaries of the fictional universe” (Scolari, 2013: 15). In other words, learners work on their receptive and active, oral and written comprehension skills, whilst participating in these innovative experiences offered by TS.

These competencies have been specifically defined by online interaction descriptors published in the Companion Volume of the *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages* (Council of Europe, 2018). This common framework is supplemented with the definition of *Key Competencies for Lifelong Learning* by the Council of Europe (2018) which specifies that, in order to develop the essential knowledge, skills and attitudes for digital competency, people must understand how digital technologies can promote communication, creativity and innovation, and be up to date on the opportunities, limitations, consequences and risks they present. The most important role for the tutor is to provide as stimulating a linguistic environment as possible, in which learning can take place without academic tuition (Council of Europe, 2018: 125). This requires teachers and students to obtain technical and didactic knowledge about the use of ICT for its effective implementation in the teaching and learning process of a foreign language.

In this respect, Rodríguez & Gómez (2017) mention that teaching English as a second language and the use of technology in teaching improve the quality of education and that nowadays both of these are converging in the classroom. According to Li (2005), by integrating technology into foreign language tuition, we are moving from a behavioural paradigm of learning to a constructionist one. Thus, 21st century education is combining the use of ICT with new teaching methodologies.

The use of narration in foreign language classrooms is nothing new. Navarro (2013) states the benefits of implementing *storytelling* in English classes, with this being one of the most popular techniques from primary school onwards and giving very positive results in foreign language lessons. *Storytelling* is the act of relaying an account filled with emotions, through the use of words and pictures. However, times are changing, with the digitalisation of classrooms and learning. With this come changes in the stories themselves and how they are being told. In this way, traditional narration takes on a new dimension, relying on new tools and supports for conveying knowledge and values that stimulate students' interest and motivation. This indicates an evolution in the teaching methodology of foreign languages, from a behaviourist perspective, a structuralist vision of language and an educational objective like grammar correction, towards an understanding of language as a vehicle of communication, in which its speakers are social agents, who may be considered at the centre of their own education when designing training courses in a globalised context (Ortiz, 2014). Transmedia storytelling involves using different media channels and thus harnessing the specific nature of each one of them to look for new interactive spaces. Boosting creativity in language learning does not need to be a complex process but, in the case of TS, it does involve redesigning methodologies beyond the physical space, with different assimilation times and moments for learners to reflect creatively.

1.3. Aim of the present study

The use of Transmedia Storytelling seems ideal for learners to develop their communicative and digital skills whilst learning a language. It could, therefore, be an alternative methodology for language education. However, there are still some unknowns: for the tutors, its type of application and for the students, how TS affects the development of their communicative competencies in a foreign language. For this reason, a qualitative synthesis is presented, which has arisen from the review of publications on the subject from 2010 to 2020. This study has two research questions:

How has Transmedia Storytelling been applied to language education?

What benefits have been described as resulting from the application of Transmedia Storytelling for foreign language learning?

The results of this analysis will indicate if there is a methodological validity to TS as an innovative element in foreign language learning.

2. Method

2.1. Objective and sample

The following procedure was followed when undertaking the literature review of articles published in the last decade about the use and pedagogical advantages of Transmedia Storytelling in language learning.

The methodology used for establishing the state-of-the-art in this field focussed on identifying and analysing a combination of sources. The emphasis was on peer-reviewed scientific articles that resonated with the objective of the research, and were indexed in databases ranked by impact factor. Next, the authors proceeded to identify the fundamental aspects in each of the articles, which permitted a deeper understanding of the central theme of this study. The articles were selected according to the quality of their research, their methodological rigour and the individual contributions of the authors. The articles were found in well-known databases, in particular: SCOPUS, ERIC and Google Scholar (see Figure 1). The keywords for the search were "Transmedia storytelling", "Transmedia storytelling + communicative competences", "Narrativas transmedia + competencias comunicativas", "Narrativas transmedia + aprendizaje de lengua extranjera", "Transmedia storytelling + second/foreign language learning". The procedure is explained in figure 1 and follows Moher et al's (2009) standardised PRISMA protocol.

Figure 1: System for identifying articles to be reviewed

The scientific publications (N=21) in this corpus were chosen according to the following selection criteria:

Theme: studies about the use of TS in education and those related to foreign language learning.

Impact: empirical studies in the form of articles published in high-impact journals after they have been evaluated by experts.

Year of publication: studies published between 2010 and August 2020.

Categorisation of analysis criteria

After the document review, experiences or proposals involving the use of TS were identified in educational environments for foreign language learning, using keywords which had previously been determined by each researcher. Once selected, the articles were classified according to the following criteria: authors, year of publication, main objective, level of education, communicative competences, country and results obtained (see table 1).

#	Authors and year of publication	Title of Article	Main Objective	Level of Education	Competences	Results Obtained	Country
1	Jenkins (2010)	Transmedia Storytelling and Entertainment: An annotated syllabus.	To describe experiences of teaching a course about transmedia entertainment and storytelling.	University students.	Media competences.	Digital practices, such as film, television, comics, advertisements, gaming and social media, and others.	United States
2	Gil-Quintana y Osuna-Acedo (2020)	Transmedia Practices and Collaborative Strategies in Informal Learning of Adolescents.	To study the habits, attitudes and strategies in informal learning related to the online transmedia skills of adolescents.	Secondary school students.	Media competences.	Independent attitude towards informal learning so that students take responsibility for their own training, thus promoting their motivation and transmedia skills.	Spain
3	Rodrigues y Bidarra (2017)	Transmedia Storytelling as an Educational Strategy: A Prototype for Learning English as a Second Language.	To identify how transmedia storytelling is being implemented in education and its relevance and suitability for learning ESL, and other subjects.	Secondary school students studying English in 10th grade.	Competences in media literacy	Relevance and suitability in the teaching of ESL and of other subjects.	Portugal
4	Perry (2020)	Multimodal Engagement through a Transmedia Storytelling Project for Undergraduate Students.	To explore the use of transmedia storytelling as a multimodal pedagogical tool for students in tertiary education.	Undergraduate university students.	Literacy competences.	Developing creativity and critical thinking; providing an active, fun and engaging atmosphere.	Malaysia

5	Alonso & Murga (2018)	Enseñar y aprender con narrativa transmedia. Análisis de experiencia en una escuela secundaria de Argentina. [Teaching and Learning with Transmedia Storytelling. Analysis of an Experience at a Secondary School in Argentina].	To reflect on Transmedia Storytelling and its implications for the educational process.	Secondary school students.	Digital competences.	Development of cognitive processes, collaborative working and reflection capacity.	Argentina
6	Roccaniti & Garland (2015)	21st Century Narratives: Using Transmedia Storytelling in the Language Arts Classroom	To explore the use of Transmedia Storytelling in art lessons, to encourage students to be active and participative readers.	Secondary school students.	Reading and digital competences.	Development of social and interpersonal skills.	United States

Reading competences

7	Teste (2012)	Transmedia in the Classroom: Breaking the Fourth Wall	To analyse the theory, design and implementation of a transmedia story.	Secondary school students (ninth and tenth grade language arts class).	Reading competences.	Motivation and putting the reader through a constructive act.	United States
8	Pence (2011)	Teaching with Transmedia	To understand the educational potential of transmedia.	Secondary school students.	Reading competences.	Significant advantages for education and motivation to read for pleasure.	United States
9	Fleming (2013)	Expanding Learning Opportunities with Transmedia Practices: Inanimate Alice as an Exemplar.	To immerse the students in an intense and motivating learning experience.	University Students.	Reading competences.	Motivation and social interaction.	United States

10	Loertscher & Wools (2014)	Transmedia Storytelling as an Education Tool.	To involve students in creative activities which encourage them to read.	Primary school students.	Reading competences.	The construction of a basic story together leads to cooperative and collaborative group work.	United States
11	Zorrilla (2019)	Recursos y prácticas transmedia en el ámbito educativo. [Transmedia resources and practices in education.]	To encourage adolescents to read as a result of a transmedia experience.	Secondary school students.	Reading competences.	Reading is encouraged and reading habits are improved.	Colombia
12	Romero & Santos (2019)	Translectura: estrategia didáctica para mejorar el proceso lector con elementos transmedia. [Transreading: didactic strategy for improving the reading process with transmedia elements.]	To improve the reading process using transmedia elements.	Junior high school students.	Reading competences.	This generated a different approach to the critical reading process.	Colombia
13	Zapata (2019)	La narrativa transmedia: Una estrategia para el fortalecimiento de la comprensión lectora. [Transmedia storytelling: A strategy for strengthening reading comprehension.]	To develop a didactic strategy for strengthening reading comprehension using transmedia storytelling.	Primary school students at Cerros de Suba Business and Technical School.	Competences and habits in reading and writing.	Strengthening of reading comprehension and development of writing skills.	Colombia

Reading competences

14	Amador-Baquiro (2018)	Educación interactiva a través de narrativas transmedia: posibilidades en la escuela. [Interactive education through transmedia storytelling: opportunities in schools.]	To research ways in which student interaction was achieved in environments supporting many communication styles.	Secondary school students.	Competences in writing.	Written output increases when students take the role of editors and producers.	Colombia
----	-----------------------	--	--	----------------------------	-------------------------	--	----------

15	Ruiz (2019)	Cyant: creación y análisis de narrativa transmedia en el aula. [Creation and analysis of transmedia storytelling in the classroom.]	To analyse the incidence of a sustained didactic proposal on the creation and analysis of transmedia storytelling in the classroom.	Students at the National Institute of Pedagogy.	Competences in writing.	Improves students' written output. Gives the tutor wide scope for addressing notions of suitability, cohesion and coherence.	Colombia
16	Balaman (2018)	Digital storytelling: A multimodal narrative writing genre.	To examine the impact of an integrated digital storytelling methodology on the (story) writing skills of students of English as a foreign language (EFL).	University students of English as a foreign language (EFL) at the School of Foreign Languages of the University of Cumhuriyet.	HSkills in writing (narratives).	Impacts on the development of students' writing skills.	Turkey

Communicative competences

17	Griffith & Bower (2013)	Transmedia in English Literature Classes: A Literature Review and Project Proposal.	To examine the function and impact of Transmedia (TM) in Higher Education and English Literature studies.	University students.	Communicative competences.	Creative expression by students and an understanding of the extraordinary creative power of digital technology.	Australia
18	Dudacek (2015)	Transmedia Storytelling in Education.	To explore young people's affinity for new technological platforms and the popularity of transmedia used in the classroom as an alternative to classical teaching methods.	Secondary school students.	Communicative competences.	Interaction with other students and tutors via ICT.	Greece

19	Munaro, & Vieira (2016)	Use of Transmedia Storytelling for Teaching Teenagers.	To verify the effectiveness of transmedia storytelling for involving teenagers in the teaching-learning process.	Secondary school students.	Communicative competences.	Motivation to use stories combined with ICT and communication.	Brazil
20	Contreras & Eguia (2017)	Transmedia Storytelling: explorando su uso en la educación. [Transmedia Storytelling: exploration of its use in education.]	o verify the effectiveness of the use of transmedia in teaching processes and to respond to the question: how effective is the use of TS in education?	University students.	Communicative competences.	Digital, textual, visual and media literacy. Develops literacies which go beyond reading and writing.	Spain
21	Saltik (2017)	Transmedia Storytelling in Education: English Language Teachers' acceptance of Application of Transmedia Storytelling to teaching contexts.	To analyse the acceptance among English teachers of the application of Transmedia Storytelling and of the adaptation to actual curricular design.	41 English teachers in 9 different countries.	Communicative competences.	Neutral stance towards the change in curriculum and the inclusion of Transmedia Storytelling in English teaching.	Portugal

Source: authors' own formulation.

3. Results

The analysis of the corpus of publications, according to the different criteria established, produces interesting results. With respect to learners' potential development of competences, the studies identify five types of skills, ranging from purely linguistic ones to those concerning technology and media. 71.43 % highlight the development of linguistic competences (communicative competences, reading and writing) and only 28.57 % reflect the emphasis on digital and media competences, as illustrated in table 2.

Table 2: Summary of competences developed

Competences developed	No. of articles	%
Media competences	4	19.05%
Digital competences	2	9.52%
Reading competences	7	33.33%
Communicative competences	5	23.81%
Writing competences	3	14.29%
	21	100%

Source: authors' own formulation.

Table 3: Summary of the period of publication

Year of Publication	No. of articles	%
2010	1	4.76%
2011	1	4.76 %
2012	1	4.76%
2013	2	9.52%
2014	1	4.76%
2015	2	9.52%
2016	1	4.76%
2017	3	14.28%
2018	3	14.28%
2019	4	19.04 %
2020	2	9.52%

Source: authors' own formulation.

In the period of publication selected (see table 3), the data confirm that since 2010 experiences have been described concerning transmedia and storytelling, in search of a new way of telling stories across multiple media and communication platforms, both in the mother tongue and in foreign languages. An increase in interest can be observed, with 19.04 % of publications being concentrated in 2019 and the first quarter of 2020. Featured themes (Figure 2) range from the transcription of educational experiences to the use of multimodal methodologies based on transmedia storytelling for foreign language learning.

Figure 2: Timeline of the evolution of TS in education and objectives of research conducted [translated version]

Transmedia Storytelling
Uses in education (2010 – 2020)

	2010 Jenkins	2010 – Description of experiences about transmedia and telling stories.
2011 – Analysis of theory, design and implementation of a transmedia story.	2011 Teske	
	2012 Pence	2012 – Understanding the educational potential of transmedia.
2013 – Exploring the function and impact of Transmedia in Higher Education and in the study of English Literature.	2013 Griffith	
	2016 Munaro & Dudeque	2016 – Verification of the effectiveness of transmedia storytelling in involving teenagers in the teaching-learning process.
2017 - Verification of the effectiveness of the use of transmedia in teaching processes and answering the question: how effective is the use of TS in education?	2017 Contreras & Eguia	
	2017 Satik	Analysis of the acceptance of Transmedia Storytelling by English teachers and modification of actual curricular design.
2018 – Reflection on Transmedia Storytelling and its implications in the educational process.	2018 Alonso & Murgia	
	2019 Ruiz	2019 – Analysis of the incidence of a sustained didactic proposal on the creation and analysis of transmedia storytelling in the classroom.
2020 – Exploring the use of transmedia storytelling as a multimodal pedagogical tool in English as a subject for tertiary education students.	2020 Shamini	

With regard to the participants (Figure 3), the majority of the studies refer to implementations in secondary school classrooms with teenagers (57.15%), followed by 28.57% of the studies, which reflect data from this educational innovation in university environments.

Figure 3: Educational level of participants in the studies

Source: authors' own formulation.

Table 4 shows the research interest in the application of Transmedia Storytelling as an educational tool, especially in some North and South American countries (63%), followed by Europe (27.3%) and only once in each of Asia and Australia.

Table 4: Articles published by country of research into the application of TS in the education sector

USA	6
Colombia	5
Spain	2
Portugal	2
Turkey	1
Malaysia	1
Greece	1
Brazil	1
Australia	1
Argentina	1

Source: authors' own formulation.

The studies analysed describe different results for the application of TS in the education sector. 25.93% mention the increase in motivation for the subject, while 22.2% note the increase in students' reading for pleasure. A smaller percentage of 7.41% indicate the benefits for writing skills, given that social interaction increases and therefore social skills are put into practice. 7.4% highlight learners' improved capacity for working collaboratively, which also influences the development of their creativity and their digital practices. Finally, only 3.7% refer to the development of students' cognitive processes and reflective capacity.

Table 5: Improvements observed after the application of TS in the education sector

Results obtained	No. of Articles	%
Motivation.	7	25.93%
Reading for pleasure	6	22.22%
Social skills and social interaction.	3	11.11%
Writing.	2	7.41%
Digital practices.	2	7.41%
Collaborative work.	2	7.41%
Creativity.	2	7.41%
Development of cognitive processes.	1	3.70%
Reflective Capacity.	1	3.70%

Source: authors' own formulation.

4. Discussion and conclusions

The majority of the studies identified concerning the educational uses of *Transmedia Storytelling* are educational research and innovation projects of an exploratory character. They are focussed on studying the uses of Transmedia Storytelling in teaching and learning in the education sector and are related to creating, developing, implementing and analysing transmedia stories. These stories are composed collectively, using various digital media, video games, films, websites, etc., whilst at the same time having educational aims.

Transmedia learning is a new concept in education, and it is being implemented at different levels of education, firstly in Secondary Education, then followed by Universities and Vocational Training Providers. Thus, it is constantly expanding. Since 2010, *Transmedia Storytelling* has been mentioned as a tool in the field of education, leaving behind teacher-centred approaches and harnessing the benefits of information and communication technologies for developing competencies. This method is providing learners with meaningful experiences, which allow them to connect with others through the use of digital resources and digital interactions.

In 2017, researchers gathered the opinions of language teachers and their acceptance of the application of TS for English teaching. In general, they had a neutral stance towards the application of Transmedia Storytelling, mainly due to the lack of knowledge of Transmedia Storytelling as a teaching tool, but also due to worries about the academic consequences of this new type of teaching. There are still few documented examples of extending the use of Transmedia Storytelling as a strategy in all foreign language teaching. However, its application has been observed in the teaching of English as a second language, where researchers recommend it for the development of linguistic, communicative and digital proficiency. In light of the above, more research is recommended to evaluate the relevance and suitability of the world of transmedia education for the purpose of learning, and also to verify whether it encourages the development of linguistic skills in other languages too.

Our qualitative synthesis confirms that the application of Transmedia Storytelling in education is being researched in different countries across the world. 26% of the studies reviewed show that, within the context of a digital culture, students are motivated to work on stories when they are combined with the use of ICT, communication and digital media. There are practical examples of studies conducted at different educational levels. On the other hand, there is confirmation that transmedia storytelling helps to engage students in creative activities which encourage them to read and write: by using cooperative group work, they construct a basic story and thus develop collaborative intelligence, reading competences (39.13%) and communicative competences (26.09%).

The use of Transmedia Storytelling in foreign language learning offers scope for the development of a wide range of pedagogical opportunities. It is recommended for engaging and educating learners and for combining methodologies for learning by doing and learning through stories. Different themes are addressed through the use of media platforms combining the art of storytelling with the use of technology, thus facilitating two-pronged learning as well as student participation. In particular, the *Transmedia Storytelling* strategy boosts the development of skills for communicating in a constantly expanding virtual community, which requires reading, interpreting, responding, thinking and contextualising contents, but it also invites us to explore the use of devices and editing programmes for pictures, audio and video.

On the other hand, integrating transmedia storytelling offers teachers an opportunity to engage their students in creative activities which encourage students to read by using cooperative group work and collaborative intelligence to construct a basic story. These changes in language learning have generated new ways of reading. According to findings by different authors in the previous sections, it is clear that the arrival of Transmedia Storytelling has had a positive impact on education and on language teaching. It influences the development of transversal competencies which allow students to connect learning from different disciplines and to deepen their autonomous learning. The use of TS implies a teaching and learning strategy that goes beyond what has come before. Its intention is to generate an experience in the user, making them the protagonist and inciting them into action, with the freedom to perform a role and integrate themselves into the story. This provides the learner with motivation, enjoyment, curiosity and positive attitudes to foreign language learning.

5. Specific contributions of each author

Contributions	Author/s
Research design	M.C. Fonseca-Mora
Documentary search	Marjorie Andrade
Data collection	Marjorie Andrade
Critical data analysis and interpretation	Marjorie Andrade y M.C. Fonseca-Mora
Review and approval of versions	M.C. Fonseca-Mora

6. Acknowledgement

Translators: Mari-Carmen Sánchez-Vizcaíno y Michal Krisko.

7. References

- [1] Aguiar, B., Velázquez, R. & Aguiar, J. (2019). Innovación docente y empleo de las TIC en la Educación Superior. *Revista ESPACIOS*, 40(02)
- [2] Alonso, E., & Murga, V. A. (2018). Enseñar y aprender con narrativa transmedia . Análisis de experiencia en una escuela secundaria de Argentina. *Comunicación y Sociedad*, (33), 203–222. <https://doi.org/ff4d>
- [3] Amador-Baquiro, J. C. (2018). Interactive education through transmedia narratives: Possibilities at school. *Magis*, 10(21), 77–94. <https://doi.org/ghp3th>
- [4] Balaman, S. (2018). Digital storytelling: A multimodal narrative writing genre. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 14(3), 202-212.
- [5] Buyse, K.& Fonseca-Mora, M.C. (eds.) (2017). Tecnologías y Segundas Lenguas. *Comunicar*, XXV (50), 1-63. <https://doi.org/10.3916/comunicar>
- [5] Cappello, M., & Walker, N.T. (2016). Visual Thinking Strategies: Teachers' reflections on closely reading complex visual texts within the disciplines. *The Reading Teacher*, 70(3), 317– 325. <https://doi.org/ft4g>
- [6] Carbonell, J. (2001). *La aventura de innovar. El cambio en la escuela*. Madrid: Morata.
- [7] Carrillo-García, M., & López, A. (2014). La teoría de las inteligencias múltiples en la enseñanza de las lenguas. *Contextos Educativos. Revista de Educación*, 0. <https://doi.org/ggwwbj>
- [8] Cendoya, Ana María; Di Bin, Verónica; Peluffo, Mercedes Virginia (2008) AICLE : Aprendizaje integrado de contenidos y lenguas extranjeras o CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning). *Puertas Abiertas*, 4 (4): 65-68. In *Memoria Académica*. Retrieved from <https://n9.cl/evurw>
- [9] Constanza, S., & Ferreira, O. (2010). Trabajo de Grado para optar por el título de Magister en Psicología-Sandra Ortega.
- [10] Council of Europe, (2001). *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [11] Council of Europe, (2018). *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment. Companion Volume with New Descriptors*. Strasbourg: Council of Europe.

- [12] Council of the European Union (2008). *Conclusiones del Consejo*, de 22 de mayo de 2008, sobre el plan de trabajo en materia de cultura. *Official Journal of the European Union*, n. C 143, 10/06/2008.
- [13] Council of the European Union. (2018). *Recomendación del Consejo*, de 22 de mayo de 2018, relativa a las competencias clave para el aprendizaje permanente. *Official Journal of the European Union*, 1–13.
- [14] Cores-Bilbao, E., Fernández-Corbacho, A., Machancoses, F.H., & Fonseca-Mora, M.C. (2019). A Music-Mediated Language Learning Experience: Students' Awareness of Their Socio-Emotional Skills. *Frontiers in Psychology*, pp. 2238. <https://doi.org/fpwm>
- [15] Contreras, R. & Eguía, J. (2017). Transmedia Storytelling: explorando su uso en la educación. *ELISAVA TEMES DE DISSENY*, (33), 26–35.
- [16] Dudacek, O. (2015). Transmedia Storytelling in Education. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 197(February), 694–696. <https://n9.cl/ul8k>
- [17] Espinosa, R. S.C (2017). Transmedia Storytelling: explorando su uso en la educación. *ELISAVA TEMES DE DISSENY*, (33), 26-35.
- [18] Fonseca Mora, M. C., & Sánchez Vizcaíno, M. C. (2020). Mediación y pensamiento crítico en el aprendizaje de lenguas: el análisis de videoclips musicales. *Revista de Estudios Socioeducativos RESED*, 8, 95–112. DOI: <https://n9.cl/v2u16>
- [19] Fonseca Mora, M.C. (2002). *Inteligencias múltiples: múltiples formas de enseñar inglés*. Sevilla: Mergablum.
- [20] Fleming, L. (2013). Ampliando las oportunidades de aprendizaje con las prácticas transmedia: Inanimate Alice como ejemplo. *Revista de educación en alfabetización mediática*, 5, 370-377.
- [21] Flores, J. F. F. (2015). Using gamification to enhance second language learning. *Digital Education Review*, (27), 32-54. Retrieved from <http://bit.ly/38dZBV7>
- [22] Fraguera-Vale, R., Pose-Porto, H. & Varela-Garrote, L. (2016). Tiempos escolares y lectura. *Ocnos: Revista De Estudios Sobre Lectura*, 15(2), 67-76. <https://doi.org/ft7w>
- [23] Griva, E. & Deligianni, A. (2017). CLIL implementation in foreign language contexts: exploring challenges and perspectives. *Research Papers in Language Teaching and Learning*, 8(2), 63-73.
- [24] Gil Quintana, J. & Osuna-Acedo, S. (2020). Prácticas transmedia y estrategias colaborativas en el aprendizaje informal de adolescentes. *Ciencias Sociales*, 9 (6), 92. <https://doi.org/ft4m>
- [25] Griffith, M. & Bower, M. (2013). *Transmedia in English Literature Classes: A Literature Review and Project Proposal*. In H. Carter, M. Gosper & J. Hedberg (Eds.), *Electric Dreams*. Proceedings ascilite
- [26] Jenkins, H. (2003). *Transmedia Storytelling*. MIT Technology Review. [Online]. Retrieved from <https://n9.cl/yml1p>
- [27] Jenkins, H. (2010). *Narración y entretenimiento transmedia: un programa de estudios anotado*, *Continuum*, 24: 6, 943-958, <https://doi.org/ft4p>
- [28] Jenkins, H., Ford, S. & Green, J. (2013). *Medios de difusión: creando valor y significado en una cultura en red*. New York: New York University Press
- [29] Li, W. (2005). The advantages of using technology in second language education. *Transforming Education through Technology Journal*, 32(10), 38-42.
- [30] Loertscher, D., & Wolls, B. (2014). *Transmedia storytelling as an education tool*. IFLA, 1–13. Retrieved from <http://library.ifla.org/881/>
- [31] Mira Giménez, M. J. (2017). Gamificación en el aprendizaje de idiomas. In C. Carbó, J. M. García & R. Lucas (Eds.) *Metodología y Evaluación de Lenguas*, 135-142. Valencia: Conselleria d'Educació, Investigació, Cultura i Esport.
- [32] Malone, T. W., & Bernstein, M. S. (2015). *Handbook of Collective Intelligence*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- [33] Maquilón Sánchez, J. J., & Hernández Pina, F. (2011). Influencia de la motivación en el rendimiento académico de los estudiantes de formación profesional. *Revista Electrónica Interuniversitaria de Formación del Profesorado*, 14 (1), 81-100. ISSN. Retrieved from <https://n9.cl/xwm5x>

- [34] Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG, The PRISMA Group (2009) Elementos de informes preferidos para revisiones sistemáticas y metaanálisis: la declaración PRISMA. *PLoS Med* 6 (7): e1000097. <https://doi.org/ghd33h>
- [35] Munaro, A. C., & Vieira, A. M. D. P. (2016). Use of Transmedia Storytelling for Teaching Teenagers. *Creative Education*, 7, 1007-1017. <https://doi.org/ft7v>
- [36] Navarro, L. (2013). *El método del Storytelling en la enseñanza de inglés en un contexto CLIL*. Bachelor's thesis. University of La Rioja. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3cYoKG4>
- [37] Ortiz, M. (2014). *Nuevas tendencias metodológicas en la enseñanza de lenguas extranjeras*: (Bachelor's thesis). University of Cádiz. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/2Os6MBC>
- [38] Perry, M. (2020). Multimodal Engagement through a Transmedia Storytelling Project for Undergraduate Students. *Revista GEMA Online*, 20, 19–40. <https://doi.org/ft7x>
- [39] Pence, H.E. (2011). Docencia con Transmedia. *Revista de Sistemas de Tecnología Educativa*, 40 (2), 131–140. <https://doi.org/ft72>
- [40] Rodrigues, P. & Bidarra, J. (2017). Transmedia Storytelling as an Educational Strategy. A Prototype of Learning English as a Second Language. *International Journal of Creative Interfaces and Computer Graphics*, 7(2), 56–67. <https://doi.org/fpwr>
- [41] Rodríguez, R. & Gómez, M. G. (2017). Competencias digitales en la enseñanza-aprendizaje del inglés en bachillerato. *Revista Campus Virtuales*, 6(2), 51-59. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/36XwMLB>
- [42] Roccanti, R., & Garland, K. (2015). 21st Century Narratives: Using Transmedia Storytelling in the Language Arts Classroom. *Signal Journal*, 38(1), 16–20. <https://doi.org/ft74>
- [43] Ruiz, L. (2019). *Cyant: creación y análisis de narrativa transmedia en el aula*. Bachelor's thesis. National Pedagogic University, Bogotá, Colombia. Retrieved from <https://n9.cl/1f79g>
- [44] Romero, S. & Santos, M. (2019). *Translectura: Estrategia Didáctica para mejorar el proceso lector con elementos transmedia*. Bachelor's thesis. Francisco José de Caldas District University, Faculty of Education. Bogotá, Colombia.
- [45] Saltik, H. (2017). *Transmedia Storytelling en educación: aceptación de los profesores de inglés de la aplicación de Transmedia Storytelling a contextos de enseñanza*. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3q8XEzS>
- [46] Scolari, C. (2013). *Narrativas transmedia: Cuando todos los medios cuentan*. *Communication Papers*, Deusto: Barcelona. <https://doi.org/ft75>
- [47] Schumann, J. H. (2000). Perspectiva neurobiológica sobre la afectividad y la metodología en el aprendizaje de segundas lenguas. In Arnold, J. (ed.) *La dimensión afectiva en el aprendizaje de idiomas*, 49-62. Madrid: Cambridge.
- [48] Sharp, L. (2017). Henry Jenkins, Sam Ford y Joshua Green, Medios de difusión: creando valor y significado en una cultura en red. *Revista de Cultura del Consumidor*, 17 (2), 454–456. <https://n9.cl/ktjuy>
- [49] Silva, J. (2010). El rol del tutor en los entornos virtuales de aprendizaje. *Innovación Educativa*, 10 (52), 13-23. ISSN: 1665-2673. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3akz2Pb>
- [50] Teske, P. R. J., & Horstman, T. (2012). Transmedia in the classroom: Breaking the fourth wall. *Proceedings of the 16th International Academic MindTrek Conference 2012: "Envisioning Future Media Environments"*, MindTrek 2012, (October 2012), 5–9. <https://n9.cl/vmmcf>
- [51] Trujillo, F. (2017). *Aprendizaje Basado en Proyectos* (3rd Edition). INTEF. *Revista Especialistas en educación*. Retrieved from <https://n9.cl/vln56>
- [52] Turan, Z., & Akdag Cimen, B. (2019). Flipped classroom in English language teaching: a systematic review. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*. <https://bit.ly/3cVIES6>
- [53] Zapata, Y. (2019). *La Narrativa Transmedia: Una estrategia para el fortalecimiento de la Comprensión Lectora*. Bachelor's thesis. National Pedagogic University, Bogotá, Colombia.
- [54] Zorrilla, M. L. (2019). Recursos y prácticas transmedia en el ámbito educativo. En Villa, M.I., Montoya Bermúdez, D. & Vásquez Arias, M. (Eds.) *Transmedia Earth Conference: medios, narrativas y audiencias en contextos de Convergencia*. Medellín: Editorial EAFIT <https://doi.org/ft79>